

AI-based Physical Layer Secret Key Exchange in Non-Terrestrial Wireless Communication Networks

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Abstract—Physical layer security is a promising technology for non-terrestrial wireless networks due to the lack of infrastructure supporting the low-altitude and high-altitude uncrewed aerial vehicle platforms. Physical layer security can be addressed using key-based and keyless approaches, such as channel adaptation and channel coding. In the key-based approach, the legitimate users generate secret keys by exploiting the unique random channel gains, which can be further used for information encryption and decryption. In non-terrestrial networks, the physical layer exploitation and the matching of generated secret keys on legitimate ends become more complex due to the 3-dimensional channel models, and the high mobility of uncrewed aerial vehicles, resulting in nonzero key. To address this challenge, this paper proposes an artificial intelligence-based key exchange mechanism where the secret keys are generated on the legitimate nodes of the communications links. The transmitter is responsible for training the neural network and transmitting the final synapses to the receiver to reconcile the information. The results are presented in terms of secret key waveforms. The success rate against the number of errors that occur in a single 128-bit key and 256-bit key shows a significant improvement.

Index Terms—Artificial intelligence, non-terrestrial networks, physical layer security, reconciliation, and secret key generation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The integration of non-terrestrial wireless communication networks (NTWCNs or NTN) with terrestrial networks (TNs) has been proposed for next-generation wireless systems as a way to enhance connectivity, particularly for high-speed users and dynamic requirements in areas like disaster-stricken, remote, and bottleneck scenarios [1]. NTN operate across different layers, enabling direct communication between satellites and ground or sea users. Uncrewed aerial vehicles (UAVs) act as aerial base stations (ABSs) or relays [2]. The integration of TNs with NTN enhances connectivity by establishing virtual

line-of-sight (vLoS). However, this integration introduces security risks for users. In traditional setups, information security is implemented across each layer of the open-system interconnection (OSI) model using both hardware infrastructure and software algorithms. In contrast, NTN, lacking conventional infrastructure, can ensure seamless security by leveraging the physical layer of wireless communications.

Neural networks (NNs) have been considered for applications in wireless networks, demonstrating their ability to be trained for adaptive repetitive tasks. Karas et al. explored an NN-based approach for secret key generation (SKG) in [3], and it has been considered for reconciliation in secret key exchange. A generative adversarial network-based SKG scheme has been presented in [4], where a channel state information (CSI) image is used for training and prediction, followed by a hash function to improve privacy. Similarly, an NN-based channel estimation algorithm, named KNEW, has been presented to generate secret keys in [5]. A novel forward NN-based adaptive quantization level prediction scheme has been proposed to determine the optimal quantization level in reconfigurable intelligent surface (RIS)-assisted communication systems utilizing channel CSI in [6]. In [7], the integrated scheduling method has been proposed to reduce the computational latency of the signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR)-based key exchange in artificial intelligence (AI) and fog computing. Similarly, an AI-based vector quantization scheme has been used in [8], while reconciliation is done through the K-mean method. Most of the work on SKG is based on the time division duplexing (TDD) system; however, for the frequency division duplexing (FDD) system, a promising deep learning-based feature mapping method of different bands has been proposed in [9]. R. Lin *et al.* proposed an SKG algorithm based on adaptive quantization and used a classical Cascade protocol for reconciliation in [10].

In physical layer security (PLS)-based SKG, most literature includes AI in channel estimation, quantization, and quantum key distribution. As a different approach, our paper introduces a novel and efficient AI-based reconciliation mechanism focused only on the SKG steps and designed to enhance communication security in both TNs and NTN. In general, reconciliation is carried out through public discussion, which

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can reveal some information to adversaries. The aim of this paper is to reduce the public discussion and to transmit only the weights of the NN for reconciliation. This method shows significant improvement over [10] based on classical non-AI-based reconciliation and [3] based on NN reconciliation.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section II describes our system, channel, and adversary models, Section III and Section IV discuss the problem of key agreement based on NN and analysis in terms of success rate and key lengths, respectively. Section V concludes the paper.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

In a wireless communications environment, establishing a secret key exchange scheme follows fundamental principles. This paper introduces a physical layer-based SKG method tailored for high-mobility aerial users. By leveraging the randomness and uniqueness of the wireless channel among users, it is proposed that secret keys can be generated in four sub-processes: (i) channel probing, (ii) quantization, (iii) reconciliation, and (iv) privacy amplification. We exploit the principle of channel reciprocity in wireless communications, where two transceivers simultaneously communicating in the same frequency range encounter identical channel characteristics. Additionally, it is assumed that the adversary is passive and positioned at a distance from both communicating devices, ensuring that the signal arriving at the adversary is uncorrelated to the signal reaching the authorized recipients, further discussed in Section II-B. This assertion holds in most real-world scenarios; more specifically, if the adversary is half of the wavelength apart, they may encounter separate fading channels [11].

A. Channel Model

To address the security threats in high-speed aerial users, orthogonal time-frequency space (OTFS) modulation is considered one of the prominent approaches due to the operation in the delay-Doppler (DD) domain. This DD domain operation makes the signal invariant to time and frequency domains and satisfies the Heisenberg uncertainty principle [12]. The channel from user 1 (U1) to user 2 (U2) is considered as h_{12} , the reciprocal channel as h_{21} . Similarly, the channels between legitimate users and eavesdroppers are considered h_{1e} and h_{2e} . All the channels are considered to follow Rayleigh fading and communicating over an additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) channel. The received signal can be written as

$$r(t) = \int \int h(\tau, v) s(t - \tau) \exp(j2\pi v(t - \tau)) dv d\tau, \quad (1)$$

where $h(\tau, v)$ is the complex baseband impulse response of the channel with v Doppler and τ delay. One key aspect of the $h(\tau, v)$ presentation is its efficiency: as only a limited amount of channel reflectors exists with corresponding Dopplers, a few parameters are required for estimating the channel in the DD domain compared to the time-frequency domain. It has significant consequences for channel estimation, equalization, and tracking, which has been further elaborated in [13]. We

considered the magnitude response function on both users for two-bit quantization to generate secret keys. We defined the magnitude response function as the ratio of the magnitude of received signal to the root-mean-square value of the received signal. Without loss of generality, the mathematical representation is given as

$$r(\cdot) = 20 \log \left(\frac{d^{-\frac{\alpha}{2}} \exp(-j2\pi d(\frac{1}{\lambda}))}{r(\cdot)_{rms}} \right) \quad (2)$$

where, d is the separation distance between U1 and U2, α is the pathloss exponent, and $r(\cdot)_{rms}$ can be written as $\sqrt{\sigma^2 + E[|r(\cdot)|]^2}$, where, σ is the standard deviation of $r(\cdot)$ and $E[\cdot]$ is the expected value. The magnitude response function is at U1 and U2, with the thresholds for analyzing the fades given in Fig. 1 showing the fading of the common channel due to multipath effects. Wireless signals are also susceptible to interference, manifesting as constructive (amplify) or destructive (attenuate). The destructive interference can cause the signal to experience temporary severe drops, referred to as deep fades.

Fig. 1. Magnitude response functions and thresholds for U1 and U2

B. Adversary Model

The adversary, eavesdropper (Eve), is assumed to be passive and able to listen and measure the channels of legitimate users. However, Eve is considered half a wavelength apart, i.e., $d_e > \lambda/2$ from both legitimate users, where d_e is the separation distance and λ is the wavelength. The d_e can be modeled as $d_e > \max\left(\frac{c}{2f_{12}}, \frac{c}{2f_{21}}\right)$, where, c is the speed of light and f is the frequency used from U1 to U2 and vice versa. Furthermore, it is assumed that Eve may know the number of occurrences of deep fades in a specific time interval. However, Eve may possibly not know the duration or the exact time instant of the deep fades. Additionally, Eve does not know the NN parameters. Both transceivers transmit a signal of predefined power. However, since in TDD, transceivers cannot transmit and receive simultaneously, they must alternate between transmitting and receiving, exchanging functions at a center frequency f_c . As mentioned, the fading characteristics observed by legitimate users remain consistent. These users proceed to generate a series of samples with a

predefined length by simultaneously sampling the magnitude response function of the received signal over a specified duration, all done with the same sampling frequency, which is equal to f_s . The maximum Doppler shift f_D in the channel is responsible for selecting f_s . In contrast, the desired computational complexity determines the number of samples. Afterwards, the transceivers apply a thresholding method to their corresponding sampled sequences, generating a bit string of the same lengths.

C. Bit String Generation

In principle, the reciprocity in real scenarios does not perfectly match due to noise, the interference introduced by other sources, and the synchronization challenges among legitimate users. Hence, the incongruities between secret keys generated by legitimate users cause disagreement in bit strings and cannot be used immediately for encryption or decryption. As shown in Fig. 2, ρ_{U1} and ρ_{U2} represent the bit string generated by U1 and U2, showing a small mismatch over a few intervals. To resolve this problem, a non-uniform quantization (NUQ) mechanism given in [14] has been adopted for M intervals with equal probability density functions (PDFs) and $M - 1$ guards strips. However, for simplicity, we considered two-bit quantization using the magnitude response function defined in Eq. 2 and plotted in Matlab from simulated data, illustrated in Fig. 1. Let ρ_{U1} be the bit string generated by exploiting the channel from U1 to U2, and ρ_{U2} is the bit string generated from the channel from U2 to U1. The sample and bit string can be represented as (i, ρ_k) , where $k \in \{U1, U2\}$. It is considered that both users apply a least-squares polynomial curve, then perform sampling and record the sampling indices S_m . The degree of the polynomial can be determined based on the Doppler shift and the sampling time frame. Both users generate a bit sequence ρ_k of length equal to the number of sampling indices l . Furthermore, a low-pass filter (LPF) is used to filter out the high-frequency components from the received signal, which can potentially affect the sensitivity. Therefore, LPF is only used for thresholding without compromising the randomness of generating keys. Thresholding has been carried out using a moving average filter (MAF) with a window size of 10 samples. Furthermore, to ensure higher entropy, the cumulative mass function (CMF) is considered equal on each side of the threshold value. Assume that $p(\cdot)$ is the probability mass function (PMF), $P(\cdot)$ is the CMF, and r_{th} is the threshold value. The P for samples above the threshold can be represented as

$$P_{r_i > r_{th}} = \sum_{i=0}^t (p(r_i > r_{th}) \quad \forall \quad p(r_i) > 0, \quad (3)$$

The CMF for the samples below threshold r_{th} is represented as

$$P_{r_i < r_{th}} = \sum_{i=0}^t (p(r_i < r_{th}) \quad \forall \quad p(r_i) > 0, \quad (4)$$

where, i in Eq. 3 and Eq. 4 represents the sample number from start time to time t . The sample lies above the r_{th} is considered

one and below as zero. The probabilities of occurrence of bit 1 and bit 0 will be uniformly distributed if $P_{r_i > r_{th}} = P_{r_i < r_{th}}$.

Both legitimate users follow the same procedure to generate secret keys; however, the mismatch of reciprocity results in a disagreement over the secret bits, named as bit mismatch probability (BMP). The BMP can be written mathematically as

$$P_{mm} = \frac{B_{mm}}{\rho_n}, \quad (5)$$

where, P_{mm} is the BMP, ρ_n is number of bits generated in time T (bits per second) and B_{mm} is the number of mismatch bits. To reduce this BMP and enable the generated keys to be used for encryption/ decryption, a reconciliation method is proposed in the following section.

III. ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE BASED KEYS AGREEMENT

The bit sequences of length l generated by U1 and U2 are ρ_{U1} and ρ_{U2} respectively. As it is considered that the eavesdropper is unaware of the channel fading of both legitimate users in Section II-B, and, hence, does not have any effect on the length and values of $\rho_{k[i]}$. The channel estimated by both users is considered highly correlated; however, the correlation factor will always be less than 1. The correlation of channels and the sampling delays ultimately affects the secret key capacity [15]. This discrepancy in correlation results in a bit mismatch of secret keys, as shown in Fig. 2. This shortcoming can be fixed through an efficient reconciliation process. Here, we present an AI-based reconciliation process described as follows.

Fig. 2. Bit strings generated by U1 and U2

For the NN formation and training, let ρ be the secret key generated by legitimate users with length L , while the length of bit strings generated by U1 and U2 is l . Therefore, the binary input of length l is given to the NN with N number of hidden nodes and L number of output nodes we get. Hence, the NN consists of three layers: the input layer with l nodes, the hidden layer with N nodes, and the output layer with L nodes, indicated as indices in Fig. 3.

The working principle of the proposed model is to generate a bit string by U1 ρ_{U1} , creating an NN with randomly initiated weights w , and randomly generating a secret key ρ of length L . The training of the NN is carried out through the training set similar to ρ_{U1} to calculate the synaptic as the output layer will remain the same. The synaptic weights of the NN at U1

Fig. 3. NN-based reconciliation

are transmitted to U2, which is then fed to the NN at U2 for the bit string generated ρ_{U2} , which the error correction codes can also follow. To maximize the secrecy of the secret key, the probability of each bit should remain the same, which means that the bits of secret keys should be uniformly distributed to enhance the entropy. The ρ can be represented mathematically as

$$\rho[L] = \sum_{i=1}^N w_{ik} \times H_i + b_1, \quad (6)$$

and

$$H_i = f\left(\sum_{j=1}^l w_{ij} \times \rho_j + b_2\right), \quad (7)$$

where $H_{i=1}^N$ is the hidden layer activation, f is the activation function, w_{ik} and w_{ij} are the input and output weight matrices associate with synapses, respectively. The terms b_1 and b_2 are the biases of the estimator of the hidden layer and input layers, respectively. We assumed the expectation of $\hat{\rho}$ is same as ρ , i.e., $E(\hat{\rho}) = \rho$. Therefore, we consider the value of b_i is zero where $i \in \{1, 2\}$.

Initially, the training set was randomly generated using Matlab to train the NN. Then, the same process, as given in Section II-C, was followed to count the number of fades in a given time duration and generate the bit string ρ_{U1} of length l . In order to train the system, the shifts in fading (which could be at the beginning of the fades or end of the fades) are introduced. The final training set can be written as follows

$$T = \{T_i^{s,n} | s \in [-S, S], n \in [1, L], i \in \{1, 2\}\}, \quad (8)$$

where S represents the maximum shift introduced in the fades, this practice is done as it is observed that the discrepancies in bit strings generated by U1 and U2 ρ_{U1} and ρ_{U2} are due to shifts in fades. Hence, the NN is trained to detect and correct the bit mismatched due to fades between legitimate users.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The magnitude response function given in Eq. 2 is initially used for bit string generation by legitimate users using a thresholding mechanism. It has been fed to the NN with 128 and 256 input and output nodes for 128-bit and 256-bit key lengths. The CMFs in Eq. 3 and Eq. 4 are taken to be equal to ensure higher entropy, i.e., $H(\rho_k)$. The output

nodes are taken unchanged, while a maximum shift of 5 in x steps is introduced in the deep fades of the magnitude response function of the received signal. The bit string was generated x times, repeatedly at the U1, ρ_{U1} used to train the NN. The synaptic weights, which were initialized manually, are updated for the output layer, while the values were kept the same for the hidden layers. The training set given in Eq. 8 was generated. During this process, the length of the random bits generated by U1 and U2, i.e., ρ_{U1} and ρ_{U2} was predefined as 128 bits and 256 bits. The learning parameter of the NN was set to 0.03, and the rectifier linear unit was used as an activation function. The repetition parameter x was set to 10. The simulation was run for 1500 epochs. The optimal value of test loss was obtained at 452 epochs, while the zero test loss was obtained at 1324 epochs. The value reaching zero validates that the NN is fully trained and able to generate secret keys with a maximum success rate. This system model is only applicable to the case where the users have highly correlated channels. The weights of the NN at U1 corresponding to ρ_{U1} are then shared with U2, initiating an identical process of deep fade shift. Subsequently, the NN, equipped with predefined nodes and the local training set, utilizes the received weights to generate the final bit string ρ_{U2} . With the assumption of the same weights of synapses for both the users, Fig. 5 shows the matched generated keys on both sides of the communications link with maximum agreement rate. Previously, the bit mismatch was observed due to shifts in fades; therefore, the shifts were considered during the generation of bit sequences to train the NN. However, the fade shift may not be regular or might be different for each user due to external interference or different noise floors.

The success rate of secret keys ρ_k generated on both U1 and U2 is analyzed against the number of errors in terms of percentage in Fig. 4. The secret key length for this analysis is chosen to be 128 bits and 256 bits. It has been observed that the success rate of key agreements decreases with the increase in the number of bits in secret keys, as illustrated in the graph in Fig. 4. The success rate is the number of fixtures of mismatched bits between legitimate users, scaled over 100. The success rate in 128-bit key length for 16-bit error is around 92 percent, and in 256-bit key length for 16-bit error is around 89 percent. Generally, it seems that the 16-bit error in a 128-bit secret key should be higher than the 16-bit error in a 256-bit lengthy key as a consequence of error probability, i.e., 16/128 and 16/256. However, it is observed that the probability of error increases with an increase in the length of the secret key due to a higher number of permutations. The number of permutations for x bit error in a 256-bit string is higher than in a 128-bit string, where $x \in \{2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, \text{and } 16\}$, also shows that the increase in x results in an increase in permutations.

The graph in Fig. 4 illustrates that the proposed system model with mobility outperforms the model presented in [3] for 128-bit and 256-bit keys. The model in [3] can only be implemented in a quasi-static TNs scenario. However, our proposed model is valid for both static and non-static scenarios in TNs and NTN. Similarly, [10] used an adaptive quantization mechanism and the Cascade protocol for reconciliation. Our

Fig. 4. Secret key agreement rate against the number of errors for 128-bit key and 256-bit key

results demonstrate an improved success rate compared to [3], which utilizes NN-based reconciliation, and [10], which employs the classical Cascade protocol-based reconciliation. While the classical protocol shows slightly better performance when the number of error bits exceeds 14 due to computational complexities. Nevertheless, our proposed method outperforms both of these approaches overall. Furthermore, Fig. 5 shows that the assumptions are appropriate for practical scenarios; however, it is observed from the graph in Fig. 4 that the higher key length results in more bit disagreement, which affects the success rate. Most importantly, both legitimate users must agree on the secret keys generated individually within the time frame of coherence. Therefore, to define the key length, a fair trade-off should be made during the SKG based on the sensitivity of wireless transmission and the computational power of the end device so as not to have an effect on the required latency.

Fig. 5. AI-based generated secret keys

V. CONCLUSION

NTNs are expected to be an important technology in next-generation wireless communication networks, particularly for

addressing connectivity and reliability challenges in remote and disaster-stricken areas. Nevertheless, ensuring information security poses a notable challenge. Leveraging physical layer-based SKG is one technique that can be employed to provide infrastructure-less and seamless security. In this context, we have introduced an NN-based reconciliation scheme to maximize key matching, minimize communication overhead, and enhance privacy. The results demonstrate that the proposed system model outperforms existing systems in terms of the success rate of generated secret keys. Future work will explore key exchange using experimental data, exploring generative adversarial networks, and implementing Frechet inception distance to evaluate the agreements in comparison with conventional techniques.

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